

LEXICO-SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF HOTEL AND TOURISM RELATED WORDS AND PHRASES

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Abstract: This article deals with the lexico-semantic analysis of related words and phrases about hotel and tourism. The most analysed words of hotel and tourism are used in terminology.

Key words: terminological, investment, vacationist, voyager, condotel, boatel.

Uzbekistan is a country with great potential in the field of tourism. There are more than 7,300 cultural heritage sites in the country, most of which are included in the UNESCO. At the same time, using the unique nature of our country, the opportunities of beautiful recreation areas, it is possible to open new tourist routes. With the active involvement of world brands in this field, we need to pay special attention to the development of pilgrimage tourism, ecological, educational, ethnographic, astronomic tourism and other sectors of the industry. In this regard, we must take into account that the use of public-private partnership opens up great opportunities for the development of the industry. Indeed, it is natural that any change in the life of society is reflected in language. The great changes taking place in Uzbekistan, the ongoing radical reforms, scientific and technological progress, close to socio-economic relations with other countries are reflected in the language. Today it is impossible to imagine different areas without terminology. Scientists have found that today there are more than 500 major fields and dozens of their major divisions, each with its own terminological system. It is no secret that in our country, too, various industries are developing rapidly, as a result of which the terminological system is also enriched. Tourism in Uzbekistan has been considered at the level of state policy since the early years of independence. All the necessary organizational and legal mechanisms for the development of the industry have been created, important normative documents have been adopted, and this work is still going on. Tourism terminology also plays an important role in the terminological system. While all changes and innovations in society are first and foremost reflected in language, processes place a number of tasks before linguists. One of these tasks is the issue of linguistic analysis of tourist terms. Today, in Uzbek linguistics there is no special collection of tourist terms. The number of terms included in existing dictionaries is not so great. For example, the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language"³² include 183 terms related to tourism. It is also important to regulate the issue of terminology in the training of leading specialists in the field, personnel who can meet world standards. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure the accelerated development of the tourism industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan"³³ states: "Quality of qualified personnel for the tourism industry, especially in the field of management and marketing It is important to radically improve the system of training, regular retraining and advanced training of tourism personnel. It is important to have in the training of textbooks, the level of availability of textbooks, strict regulation of industry terms. One of the important tasks of Uzbek

terminology is the linguistic study of the tourist terminology of the Uzbek language, the creation of an explanatory dictionary of terms. Tourism has entered in this millennium with the prospect of continued expression and greater importance in the world economy, facing many challenges. The significance of tourism is recognized in both developed and developing and beneficial agent of both economic and social change. Indeed, tourism has stimulated employment and investment, modified land use and economic structure, and made a positive contribution of the balance of payment in many countries throughout the world. This ever expanding spirit of travel has lived on down the ages. From the very early historic period, travel has had a fascination for man. Much of the travel in the beginning was eagerly unconscious and rather a simple affair. This unit will give a detail of travel pattern through the ages.

Synonyms of the word "tourist"³⁴

TOURIST	sightseer	экскурсант	sayyoh
	traveller	путешественник	sayohatchi
	tourer	турист	sayyoh
	wayfarer	путник	yo'lovchi
	wanderer	странник	adashgan
	tripper	путешественник	sayohatchi
	globetrotter	путешественник	sayohatchi (dunyo bo'ylab)

In this table we can see the synonyms of the word tourism. In English, the word tourist has more synonyms than in Uzbek, due to the fact that tourism in European countries is better developed than in Asian countries, and the sources of enrichment of the English language are relatively large. Other synonyms are voyager, journeyer, jet-setter, vacationist, excursionist, rubberneck, sightseer, passenger, vacationer, visitant. We can use these synonyms depending on the place of speech, some can be used in literary, conversational, journalistic styles while others can be divided into formal and informal types.

HOTEL	rotel	ротель	Rotel
	Star hotels	Звездные отели	yulduzli mehmonxonalar
	commercial hotels	коммерческие отели	savdo mehmonxonalar
	bungalow	бунгало	Bungalov
	eurotel	евротель	Yevrotel
	pensions	пенсии	pensiyalar
	condominium	кондоминиум	kondominyum
			kapsulali

There are so many words that describe a hotel in English, customers have the opportunity to choose the hotel they like based on their wishes. As the tourism industry develops day by day, new words about the hotel are also being adopted. Since English is an analytical language, it is an effective method of loading various new lexical and grammatical meanings into a word by adding words along with conjugation.

Words that do not have an independent lexical meaning in the following terms are added to the lexeme and give it a new meaning: Non-refundable (non-refundable service or goods), non-transferable (nontransferable service type in the name of the person, other than the person who made the order) *on-line* (the journey carried out on an aircraft of an airline) *off-line* (the journey completed through the exchange of airline companies and aircraft) *duty-free*(tax-exemptgoods).

ex gratia payment (voluntary / non-compulsory payment) *in-house laundry* (hotel laundry service), in-flight entertainment (entertainment during flight), in-flight magazines (magazines in the airplane) *add-on* (not published in the Travel brochure, a service that requires an additional fee) *layover, stopover* (when air route is changed, a short waiting time) *drive-in restaurant* ↔ *drive-through restaurant* (a restaurant that supplies orders to car owners who are in a parking lot ↔ a restaurant that provides orders to visiting car owners inside or through a window) The prefix “de-” is effective in forming travel fees, which form a downward movement from the vehicle. The prefixes “en-“, ‘em-“ are a functional antonym to it, or rather represent an exit (ride)to the types of transport: *Embark* ↔ *disembark* (to get onto a vehicle – to get off vehicle) *Embus* ↔ *debus* (to get onto a bus – to get off a bus) *Enplane* ↔ *deplane* (to get onto a plane – to get off a plane) the opportunity to choose the hotel they like based on their wishes. As the tourism industry develops day by day, new words about the hotel are also being adopted.

One of the specific word-building methods available in English language is blending. In this linguistic phenomenon, parts of two or more words are united and a new word is formed, which creates a common understanding from the meaning elements of all. Among the terms tourism, one can also come across words that are a derivative of this method:

dinkies = *double* + *income* + *no* + *kids*

motel = *motor* + *hotel*

brunch = *breakfast* + *lunch*

condotel = *condominium* + *hotel*

boatel = *boat* + *hotel*

apartotel = *apartment* + *hotel*

This phenomenon is also exists in the names of countries that are the developers of the tourism industry. For example, such as Eurasia, Australasia, Polynesia, Melanesia Most of the terminology of English Tourism came into being through the formation of a word combination of two or more vocabulary words (for example, altitude sickness, familiarization trip, bell captain, boutique hotel, hotel tariff, health club and many others). Alternatively, the case of the application of a component in the form of an abbreviation between such compound words as this is also considered a phenomenon. We can see this on the example of fam (familiarization) trip, e-

(electron)-booking, eco(ecological)tourism, agro (agricultural) tourism, auto (automobile) strada samples. “Adjective/qualitative+noun” combinations are also well spread.

For example, such as lodging industry, paying guest, late check-out, plastic money, transit passenger, connecting rooms, green holidays and so on.

In conclusion, the lexical-semantic analysis of words and phrases related to tourism and hotel is analyzed. During the formation of the terminology of English Tourism, the cause of various linguistic and extra-linguistic phenomena was bleached, subjected to the influence of a new concept of Tourism and, as a result, languages that contributed to the new term, acquired lexical-semantic features worth of observation. First of all, it would be correct to analyze the lexical peculiarities of the terms. Since English is an analytical language, it is an effective method of loading various new lexical and grammatical meanings into a word by adding words along with conjugation.

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